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Performance of SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP Risk Algorithms in a Cypriot Cohort

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Abstract

Background

SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP algorithms and associated online calculators provide a new and easy method of estimating the 10-year cardiovascular risk in apparently healthy Europeans. The aim of the study was to determine the performance of these algorithms in terms of discrimination and calibration in the cohort of the Cyprus Epidemiological Study on Atherosclerosis (CESA), not only for the 10-year risk for myocardial infarction (MI), stroke and cardiovascular death, but also for all types of atherosclerotic cardiovascular events (ASCVE).

Methods

SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP for low-risk regions were calculated in a non-diabetic subset of CESA consisting of 908 people (mean age \pm SD: 57.8 \pm 10.5; range 40-89; 58.8% female) using baseline risk factors. Mean follow-up was 13.2 \pm 3.7 years (range 1-17) with 89 primary endpoints (MI, stroke and cardiovascular death) and 136 secondary endpoints (primary endpoints, angina, cardiac failure, coronary revascularisation, transient ischaemic attack, claudication and critical limb ischaemia).

Results

The C-statistic for the prediction of the primary endpoint for all ages was 0.76 (95% CI 0.70 to 0.81) and the observed 10-year event rate was similar to the predicted one. However, the observed 10-year rate for secondary events was similar to the estimated one only when the algorithm for high-risk regions was used.

Conclusion

SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP moderate risk algorithms performs well in the Cypriot population for predicting the 10-year risk for MI, stroke and fatal cardiovascular disease. However, an estimate of the 10-year risk for all ASCVD events is best calculated from the high-risk algorithm.

Keywords

SCORE2, SCORE2-OP, performance, Cypriot cohort

Introduction

The development of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD) is the result of several interacting genetic, physiological, social and environmental risk factors (1). Risk estimation for individuals free of ASCVD is currently based on several conventional basic risk factors such as age, gender, blood pressure, smoking, blood lipids and diabetes. Other risk factors such as body mass index, family history of ASCVD, antihypertensive treatment and high sensitivity C-reactive protein have also been used in some risk estimation systems (2). Prevention efforts have been highly promoted in recent years and evidence shows that 50% of the reductions in mortality from coronary heart disease are related to changes in risk factors and 40% to improved treatments (3). Risk stratification is a useful tool to determine not only who is likely to benefit from prophylactic therapy, but also how aggressive such therapy should be in relation to age and risk level (4). In this way optimum therapy may be provided aiming for maximum benefit in a most cost-effective way.

For asymptomatic individuals in the absence of diabetes without any history of ASCVD the algorithms of SCORE2 for those 40-69 years (5) and SCORE2-OP for those 70-89 years (6) with their associated online calculators (<https://u-prevent.com>) provide a new and easy means of estimating the 10-year risk for myocardial infarction (MI), stroke or cardiovascular death in European individuals. Cardiovascular death includes death due to coronary heart disease, heart failure, ischemic stroke, and sudden death.

The aim of the study presented in this paper was to determine the performance of SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP algorithms in terms of discrimination and calibration in the cohort of the Cyprus Epidemiological Study on Atherosclerosis (CESA) (7,8) not only for the 10-year risk for myocardial infarction (MI), stroke or cardiovascular death but also for all types ASCVD.

Methods

CESA is a prospective cohort study of ASCVD in 1102 individuals aged 40 years or more (7,8).

Recruitment

Baseline data have been collected from the residents of two mountain villages, a third village in the outskirts of the capital, and their immediate relatives and relatives of their spouses who lived in any one of the main towns or other villages. These sites were randomly selected by having a blindfolded person throw darts at a map of Cyprus. All inhabitants, male and female, of the above villages were

identified through the population list held at the mayor's office and all those aged 40 or older were invited to participate. The overall participation rate at baseline was 95%. The study was approved by the ethics committee of the Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics. All participants provided written informed consent. Recruitment occurred over a 5-year period (2003-2008). Baseline characteristics of the first 767 recruited individuals were reported in 2009 (7). The value of ultrasonographic measurements of atherosclerotic plaques present in the carotid and common femoral bifurcations on ASCVD risk stratification was reported in 2022 (8).

Clinical and biochemical data collection

A full medical history was taken, and a physical examination was made with emphasis on conventional cardiovascular risk factors and symptoms including angina, myocardial infarction, ischemic neurological events and intermittent claudication. All past and current medications were recorded as well as height and weight measurements and a sitting blood pressure, measured three times with the first measurement being discarded. An ECG was performed in order to detect arrhythmias or ischaemia. A fasting (8-12 hours) blood sample was obtained for serum total cholesterol, LDL-cholesterol, HDL-cholesterol, triglycerides and glucose estimations.

Follow-up

Annual contact was made with an initial telephone call to individuals and their relatives by a trained researcher. If any health-related events were reported, the family doctor or hospital were contacted for validation from records and death certificates. The last annual follow-up was in 2020.

Outcomes

The primary outcome of atherosclerotic cardiovascular events (ASCVE) was a composite of myocardial infarction (MI), stroke or cardiovascular death. Cardiovascular death included death due to coronary heart disease, heart failure, ischemic stroke and sudden death. A secondary outcome was a composite of MI, onset of angina, coronary artery revascularization, ischemic stroke, transient ischemic attack (TIA), onset of claudication or critical limb ischemia and cardiovascular death.

MI was based on history and hospital documentation, including information on coronary artery intervention. The diagnosis of angina was based on the history and confirmatory hospital investigations including ECG or thallium stress tests. The diagnosis of ischemic stroke and TIA was based on the patient's history, hospital records, CT- or MRI-Brain scans and reports from

neurologists who saw the patient. Intermittent claudication was based on the history of recurrent pain on walking at a fixed distance in the presence of weak or absent pulses and ankle/brachial systolic blood pressure index less than 0.9. Cause of death was determined using death certificates, hospital records and information from the family doctor.

Study exit-points

Follow-up ceased with the first occurrence of any of the following: the first primary or secondary outcome measure, death from causes other than ASCVD or loss to follow-up. Individuals lost to follow-up were included in the analysis for all years up to the time of loss.

Statistical analysis

Baseline clinical and biochemical features in the subjects of the CESA who did not have any ASCVD or diabetes were tabulated as mean \pm SD for continuous variables normally distributed, median and interquartile ranges for continuous variables with skewed distribution and as percentages for categorical variables.

The SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP online calculators (<https://u-prevent.com/calculators/score2>) were used to calculate the 10-year individual risk using both the moderate and high-risk regions. Baseline data on risk factors were entered online obtaining the values for moderate risk and high-risk regions at the same time. This was repeated one month later by the same person so that any data entry errors could be corrected.

Individual subjects were classified into five risk classes according to the predicted 10-year risk from SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP algorithms for moderate and high 10-year risk regions as follows: Class 1: risk <5%; Class 2: 5-10%; Class 3: 10-20%; Class 4: 20-30%; and Class 5: >30%.

The 10-year observed MI/Stroke/cardiovascular death rate for each of the five classes was determined from Kaplan-Meier lifetables. This observed event rate was plotted against the predicted classes.

The 10-year risk for the observed secondary endpoint of all ASCVD events (MI, onset of angina, coronary artery revascularization, ischemic stroke, transient ischemic attack [TIA], onset of claudication or critical limb ischemia) was also plotted against the predicted risk classes based on the algorithms for both moderate-risk regions and high-risk regions.

Results

Selection of subjects

A total of 1102 people were recruited during the years 2003-2008 and followed-up till 2020. Individuals over the age of 89 years, those with a history of clinical ASCVD at the time of recruitment and those with diabetes mellitus were excluded from the analysis presented in this paper in line with the design of SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP. Twenty-eight (2.8%) participants were lost to follow-up at different times and were included in the analysis until the date they were lost to follow-up. The mean \pm SD of the follow-up index was 0.98 \pm 0.09. Thus, a total of 908 individuals without ASCVD or diabetes aged 40 to 89 (mean age \pm SD 57.8 \pm 10.5; 55.8% female) at baseline were included into the analysis. Follow-up was for a mean 13.2 \pm 3.7 years (range 1-17). The distribution of the residence of the 908 persons studied is shown in Figure 1 and the baseline characteristics are summarised in Table 1.

Primary and secondary Outcomes

There was a total of 89 fatal or non-fatal primary outcomes: myocardial infarction in 59, ischemic stroke in 29 and cardiac failure in one. There were 136 ASCVE (composite secondary outcome): MI in 59, ischemic stroke in 29, cardiac failure in one, onset of angina in 12, coronary angioplasty/stenting in 8, coronary artery bypass in 19, onset of intermittent claudication in 7 and critical lower limb ischemia in 1. The mean \pm SD length of time between recruitment and event was 8.36 \pm 4.1 years.

Other Outcomes

There were 72 other causes deaths (23 due to malignancy and 49 due to other non-ASCVD events).

Association between risk scores and observed events

The range and distribution of SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP risk for moderate risk regions in the CESA cohort is shown in Figure 2A. The distribution of SCORE2 in those aged 40-69 and its comparison to the expected distribution in the SCORE2 publication (5) for women and men is shown in Figure 2B and 2C respectively.

The area under the ROC curve for the prediction of MI/Stroke/Cardiovascular death (primary outcome) for all ages using SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP algorithms was 0.76 (95% CI 0.70 to

0.81). The observed MI/Stroke/Cardiovascular death cumulative rate in the five predicted risk classes (< 5%, 5-10%, 10-20%, 20-30% and > 30%) was obtained by Kaplan-Meier life table analysis shown in Figure 3A. Figure 3B is a plot of the observed 10-year cumulative MI/Stroke/Cardiovascular Death rate against the predicted risk classes. The slope indicates that the observed rate is very close to the predicted rate.

The area under the ROC curve for the prediction of all ASCVE using SCORE2/SCORE2-OP risk for moderate-risk regions was 0.74 (95% CI 0.69 to 0.78). The observed cumulative rate for all ASCVD events in the five predicted risk classes is shown in Figure 4A. Figure 4B is a plot of the observed 10-year cumulative ASCVD event rate against the predicted risk classes. The slope indicates that the observed rate is higher than the predicted rate. For example, in the predicted Class 3 with mean predicted event rate of 15% the observed event rate is 22% representing a 47% increase.

The area under the ROC curve for the prediction of all ASCVD events using SCORE2/SCORE2-OP risk algorithm for **high-risk regions** was 0.73 (95% CI 0.69 to 0.78). The observed cumulative rate for all ASCVD events in the five predicted risk classes is shown in Figure 5A. Figure 5B is a plot of the observed 10-year cumulative ASCVD event rate against the predicted risk classes. The slope indicates that the observed rate is close to the predicted rate.

Discussion

The SCORE2 algorithm was based on 677,648 individuals from 45 prospective cohorts in 13 countries and was recalibrated for different European regions for low, moderate, high and very high risk using estimated age- and sex-specific contemporary incidences and risk factor distributions. External validation was obtained from 25 additional cohorts in 15 European countries (5).

SCORE2-OP was derived from the Cohort of Norway (CONOR) which involved 28,503 individuals and was recalibrated to the same four geographical risk regions mentioned above, also using estimated age and sex specific incidences and risk factor distributions. External validation was obtained from five different prospective cohorts (6). Thus, the online risk calculators and charts provide a different risk for each predefined risk-region. For example, Spain, France, UK and Norway are low risk; Cyprus, Greece, Germany and Sweden are moderate risk; Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia and Turkey are high risk; and eastern European countries and Syria are very high risk (4,5).

The results obtained from the Cyprus cohort indicate that the 10-year MI, stroke or cardiovascular mortality rate as estimated by SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP for moderate risk regions

in the CESA cohort corresponds closely to the observed event rate (Figure 3) with a C-statistic of 0.74 (95% CI 0.70 to 0.81). However, the distribution of the 10-year risk in the subgroup of those aged 40-69 appears to be shifted to the right compared with the expected one published in the SCORE2 paper (5) (Fig. 2B and 2C). The number of people in the <2.5% 10-year risk category is nearly 40% less and the number of people in the 5-10% risk category is increased by more than 50%. This shift to the right is more obvious in men. Age is a major factor that determines the distribution of risk in a population, and it may account for this shift. Although a Greek cohort (ATTICA) was used in the derivation of the SCORE algorithms, as far as we know a calibration on a Cypriot cohort has not yet occurred. The mean age of the CESA cohort and the prevalence of other risk factors were closer to the mean values in the total number of cohorts used to derive SCORE2 than those from the Greek ATTICA cohort (5) (Table 1).

The observed 10-year risk for all ASCVD was much higher than the risk estimate obtained from SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP (Fig. 4B). This is not surprising because SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP are designed to predict 10-year risk for MI, stroke or cardiovascular death. However, it was very close to the 10-year risk obtained from SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP for high-risk regions when the latter was applied to the CESA cohort (Figure 5) with C-statistic of 0.73 (95% CI 0.69 to 0.78). This finding suggests that for the Cypriot population SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP algorithms for high-risk regions may be used to estimate the risk for all ASCVD events.

A limitation of our study is that the CESA may not be truly representative of the Cyprus population despite the wide distribution of place of residence (Figure 1). Another limitation is that the cohort is relatively small, and a larger cohort may be needed for derivation of multiplication factors needed for calibration.

Despite the above limitations and until other studies with a larger number of persons become available our data suggest that the SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP moderate risk algorithms performs well in the Cypriot population for predicting the 10-year risk for MI, stroke or fatal cardiovascular disease. An unexpected finding is that an estimate of the 10-year risk for all ASCVD events may be obtained from SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP using the algorithm for high risk regions.

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Conflict of interest: None

Association with industry by the authors: None

Data availability statement: Deidentified data used for the study presented in this paper are available for inspection in an SPSS database. This can be obtained from the authors. Follow-up to the 17th year has been included in the data presented.

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Table 1. Baseline clinical and biochemical features in 908 individuals of the Cyprus Epidemiological Study on Atherosclerosis (CESA) aged 40-89 and free of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD) or diabetes mellitus at recruitment.

Variable	CESA Cohort	Greek ATTICA Cohort	Mean of Cohorts used in SCORE2
Continuous variables (normal distribution; mean \pmSD)			
Age (years)	57.8 \pm 10.5	53 \pm 10	57 \pm 9
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.7 \pm 4.7		
SBP (mmHg)	137.0 \pm 16.5	128 \pm 19	136 \pm 19
DBP (mmHg)	83.7 \pm 10.0		
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	226.4 \pm 41.3	204.0 \pm 38.5	223 \pm 42.3
HDL-Cholesterol (mg/dL)	51.4 \pm 13.0	48.1 \pm 15.4	55 \pm 15.4
LDL-Cholesterol (mg/dL)	140.0 \pm 31.7		
Continuous variables (skewed distribution; median and interquartile range)			
SCORE2/SCORE2-OP Moderate-risk region	5% (3.2,9.6)		
SCORE2/SCORE2-OP High-risk region	7.4% (3.6,12.5)		
Categorical variables	Number of subjects (%)		
Gender: Female	506 (55.8%)	51%	44%
Smoking at entry	207 (22.8%)	41%	15%
Atrial fibrillation	6 (0.8%)		
Hypertension	256 (28.2%)		
Antihypertensive therapy	248 (27.3%)		
Lipid lowering therapy	115 (12.7%)		

Antiplatelet therapy	66 (7.3%)
BMI = Body Mass Index; SBP = Systolic Blood Pressure; DBP = Diastolic Blood Pressure	

Figure 1

Distribution of the areas of residence of the 908 persons studied. Size of red areas is proportional to the number of persons included in the study. Population in north-western part of the island under Turkish control was not available.

A

B**Figure 2 A,B,C**

Distribution of SCORE2/SCORE2-OP for moderate risk regions in the Cyprus Epidemiological Study on Atherosclerosis (CESA). A. Frequency distribution of SCORE/SCORE2-OP. B and C. Distribution of 10-year risk for MI, Stroke and cardiovascular death according to SCORE2 in ages 40-69 of women (B) and men (C) using baseline risk factors (blue) in CESA cohort compared with the expected distribution in the Cyprus population as published by the SCORE2 working group and ESC Cardiovascular Risk Collaboration (orange) (Fig. 5 in Ref 5).

Figure 3

A. Observed cumulative MI/Stroke/CV Death rate (%) in the five predicted risk classes using SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP for moderate risk regions. B. Observed 10-year cumulative MI/Stroke/CV Death rate plotted against SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP for moderate-risk regions (Class 5 not shown). Dotted line indicates perfect agreement. Class 1: risk <5%, observed risk 2% (95% CI 0.85% to 3.9%), N=382; Class 2: risk 5-10%, observed risk 7% (95% CI 4.4% to 10.2%), N=309; Class 3: risk 10-20%, observed risk 14% (95% CI 9.2% to 20.0%), N=177; Class 4: risk 20-30%, observed risk 28% (95% CI 15.0% to 51.0%), N=28; Class 5: risk >30%; observed risk 51% (95% CI 21.1% to 78.9%), N=12.

Figure 4

A. Observed cumulative ASCVD event rate (%) in the five predicted risk classes using SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP for moderate-risk regions. B. Observed 10-year cumulative ASCVD event rate plotted against SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP for moderate-risk regions (Class 5 not shown). Dotted line indicates perfect agreement. Class 1: risk <5%, observed risk 2% (95% CI 0.85% to 3.9%), N=382; Class2: risk 5-10%, observed risk 11% (95% CI 7.7% to 15.0%), N=309; Class 3: risk 10-20%, observed risk 22% (95% CI 16.1% to 28.9%), N=177; Class 4: risk 20-30%, observed risk 31% (95% CI 21.1% to 41.2%), N=28; Class 5: risk >30%; observed risk 51% (95% CI 31.1% to 70.9%), N=12.

A

B

Figure 5

A. Observed cumulative ASCVD rate (%) in the five predicted risk classes using SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP for high-risk regions. B. Observed 10-year cumulative ASCVD rate plotted against SCORE2 and SCORE2-OP for high-risk regions (Class 5 not shown). Dotted line indicates perfect agreement. Class 1: risk <5%, observed risk 3% (95% CI 1.4% to 5.5%), N=322; Class2: risk 5-10%, observed risk 10% (95% CI 6.6% to 14.5%), N=255; Class 3: risk 10-20%, observed risk 14% (95% CI 9.9% to 19.1%), N=238; Class 4: risk 20-30%, observed risk 25% (95% CI 19.6% to 31.0%), N=69; Class 5: risk >30%; observed risk 52% (95% CI 30.9% to 72.6%), N=24.

